

THEIA^{XR} NEWSLETTER

ISSUE No. 2

UPDATE ON THEIA^{XR}

Welcome to the second issue of the THEIA^{XR} Newsletter, where we provide you a status of our activities and take a look at many events and meetings that took place in the past half year. A lot has happened, and many activities are in the queue, and we are thrilled to share some of these with you.

Martijn Rooker, THEIA^{XR} project coordinator states:

“The project has made significant progress in all domains and technologies. First prototypes are available, and first tests have been performed that have shown significant progress. It is great to see how motivated the partners are and it is fascinating to see how various XR technologies can be applied in this new domain, supporting the operators of these machines!”

CO-DESIGN: BE PART OF THEIA^{XR}

Figure 1: Co-Design Methodology

CO-DESIGN METHODOLOGY

Within our project, we are following a transdisciplinary co-design methodology, involving all critical user- and stakeholder groups and scientific and technical partners as experts in their respective fields. The methodology consists of four phases:

- (1) Analysis – Understanding how operators work with the vehicles
- (2) Co-Design – Developing concepts for the vehicle cabin together with operators
- (3) Experience Prototyping – Turning concepts into tangible demonstrators
- (4) Co-Evaluation – Testing demonstrators and gathering operator feedback

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We are currently in the second phase, working together with real vehicle operators to gather their feedback and new ideas for ideal cabin technologies of the future. All snow grooming, logistics and construction operators are highly welcome to participate in our Co-Design process and shape with us technologies we are developing.

CALL FOR OPERATORS

Three different application domains have been selected that pose various challenging tasks and environments for the human operator controlling the machinery. All machines within the use cases are high-tech machines, requiring much experience controlling them and the continuous attention of the operator.

SNOWGROOMING

A snow groomer needs to be operated in all conditions, including bad weather situations or even a whiteout scenario. We envision a future where sensors and visualization assistances support the operator in precise, efficient and safe snow grooming operations, even during fog or snowstorms.

LOGISTICS

Reach stackers, representing the logistics use case, are handling heavy cargo such as 20 – 40ft containers and truck trailers in busy harbour or railway terminals, sharing the narrow corridors with trucks and other vehicles. Thus, it is necessary to provide the human operator with an ideal perception of the task at hand, the load they are carrying and their environment.

CONSTRUCTION

Operators in construction need to handle heavy excavators and similar machines safely in difficult terrain, paying attention not only to their tasks, but also other vehicles, workers and bystanders in their surroundings. Mixed-reality technologies will aid the human operator in controlling the machine and efficiently navigating in the operating environment.

Whether operators are currently in training, have a significant experience or are acting as trainers – they all bring significant expertise that is of high value for our project.

The input is given via our co-design platform (online). To find out more about the co-design and how to participate, please visit our [website](#).

Figure 2: Call for Operators

UPDATES FROM WORK PACKAGES 2 and 3

WP2 REQUIREMENTS, USE CASE AND DEMONSTRATOR SPECIFICATION

*Author: Anastasia Sergeeva,
Université du Luxembourg*

Within the frames of WP2, we conducted a series of activities that helped us to elicit and formulate the privacy requirements we should adhere to throughout the project. Using a methodological approach called LINDDUN GO, developed at KU Leuven, Anastasia Sergeeva and Claudia Negri-Ribalta from the University of Luxembourg led a series of online workshops with stakeholders. Additionally, we furthered our understanding of the users' perspectives by analysing the privacy-related outcomes of contextual inquiries and privacy audit surveys completed by the project members.

This combined approach enabled us to identify key privacy challenges specific to our project's context. The insights from the workshops and surveys were meticulously analysed and utilized to refine our privacy requirements. Our iterative process ensured that the privacy measures we plan to implement are not only theoretically sound but also practically relevant to our users.

In addition to technical measures, we are also focusing on raising awareness among our consortium members and stakeholders about the importance of privacy and data protection even beyond the exact scope of the project to be sure that we can foresee the privacy risks which can occur during the exploitation of the results of the project. This involves facilitating discussion sessions within privacy workshops and developing design recommendations for XR-related technologies in specific workplaces, such as Off-Highway Machinery.

WP3 TRANSDISCIPLINARY CO-DESIGN

In WP3, we moved from the analysis phase to the co-design of technology concepts. The results we had gathered from user research in Italy (snow grooming), Sweden (logistics) and Germany (construction) were summarized in so-called “problem scenarios”. These problem scenarios are written like stories from the perspective of fictional operators, outlining typical workdays of vehicle operators to provide everyone with easily graspable descriptions of how tasks are currently handled in each use-case and how problematic or dangerous situations may arise.

Based on these problem scenarios, we conducted ideation workshops in late 2023 with consortium partners in each use-case to collect initial technology ideas and assess their usefulness and feasibility. These ideas were then integrated into what we call “vision scenarios” in the project, stories that outline how we envision vehicle operation in the future.

*Author: Manuel Kulzer, Stuttgart
Media University*

In early 2024, we started planning co-design workshops with vehicle operators. In February, we travelled to Italy again to discuss our vision scenarios with snow-groomer operators. We held two co-design

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workshops in which asked the operators for their opinions on each idea we proposed, noting down which ones they approved and where they had change requests. In the second phase of the workshops, we asked the operators to scribble their ideas of what the previously discussed features should look like from the cabin perspective. The operators' feedback and ideas will be used to develop the next stage of scenarios – so-called “information scenarios” outlining the content and appearance of information visualizations in the cabin, which will also be validated in another round of workshops. However, for now, our focus is on validating and elaborating the vision scenarios for the other use-cases as well. For March 2024, we have scheduled two more visits to a construction machine training centre in Germany, where we will meet experienced excavator operators and trainees.

Parallel to the progress of the co-design approach, first steps in prototype and demonstrator development have been taken. Both “real” tangible and virtual simulations of snow-groomer, reach stacker and excavator cabins are in development and preparations for prototype tests are underway. For the co-evaluation, we have prepared several multilingual questionnaires to measure relevant WP3 KPIs: GSE (perceived self-efficacy), QUESI (perceived intuitiveness of the system), SART (situation awareness), Uneeds (psychological need fulfilment) and WAMI (perception of meaningfulness). These and more will be measured for the current reality of vehicle operation and for our final cabin demonstrators to see if our technology concepts facilitate the expected improvements.

PAST MEETINGS AND EVENTS

September 2023: OPERATOR WORKSHOP

At the beginning of September, Stuttgart Media University researcher Tanja Brodbeck visited our project partner Kalmar in Finland to gain initial insights into how reachstacker operators work.

In particular, the visit to the Hanko port site provided important impressions for this: Even on this comparatively quiet day, it was possible to get an idea of how much movement of machines, vehicles and people of different sizes takes place there and what challenges this entails.

The following statement by an operator sums up the biggest safety-relevant problem very well: "On the road, you are the biggest road user with your car. On the port area, you are the smallest road user with your car".

In addition, the blind spots of the different vehicles can be so unfavourable to each other that the already limited visibility becomes even smaller and even more risk results. This is where our THEIA^{XR} project comes in particularly well:

With the aim of making the invisible visible, this is a particularly good place to start to bring about a great improvement for reachstacker operators and all other people on the port area.

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Figure 3: Hanko port, Finland

Tanja Brodbeck also gained exciting insights into the remote control of cranes and automated terminals at the KALMAR test site. This gives a glimpse into the future, where the logistics industry can develop with the help of new technologies.

OCTOBER 2023: OPEN LAB NIGHT @TU GRAZ

On October 4th, the Graz University of Technology Institute of Computer Graphics and Vision opened its doors for an open lab night. The goal was to present the institute and some running projects to students interested to pursue their bachelor / master / PhD thesis with the institute. THEIA^{XR} was one of the projects presented to the students, using disco-hardware to visualize the solution to practical problems in industrial environments. The high-power laser projectors were projecting driving information on to the surface of a building, mirroring the experience of operators of large off-highway machinery such as the snow groomer. The team around Maximilian Tschulik, Mika Heinemann, Thomas Kernbauer and Clemens Arth was answering questions from interested participants, who engaged in vivid discussions throwing in ideas on how to further investigate the problem statement presented.

Clemens Arth, TUG: *"The R&D work in THEIA^{XR} is an excellent example how to develop ideas under laboratory conditions and how to subsequently evaluate these concepts in real-world scenarios. At the end, it is the real-world problems that matter, and our aim is to develop and move as much tech as possible out of the lab into the field."*

This open lab night was an excellent matchmaking place between members of the EU project team and students and we're looking forward to the further exchange.

Figure 4: Open lab night @ TUG

OCTOBER 2023: STEREOPSIA

Upon invitation of DG CNECT and XR4Europe, THEIA^{XR} was part of the Session "PRESENTATION OF HORIZON EUROPE & H2020 PROJECTS". Martijn Rooker presented the project and the current status of activities.

Figure 5: Martijn Rooker during his presentation

The session covered a wide range of projects, each targeting different aspects and use cases to be addressed with the support and further enhancement of XR solutions.

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Figure 6: Martijn Rooker presenting the THEIA^{XR} project

Besides the core technical topics, further very important key success criteria have been addressed and discussed:

- ◆ ethical use of XR solutions and the data generated
- ◆ privacy issues and corresponding concerns
- ◆ end user acceptance

OCTOBER 2023: MEETING SISTER PROJECTS

At the Stereopsia Conference it was also time to share best practise, exchange experience and draft plans together, when sister projects got together and the Horizon Europe and H2020 project presentation.

Figure 7: Didier Stricker, Martijn Rooker, Giuseppe Amato and Fabio Perossini

Martijn Rooker representing THEIA^{XR}, Didier Stricker representing the [Sharespace.EU](#) project and Fabio Perossini and Giuseppe Amato for the [SUNxr.he](#) project came together to discuss the

status of the activities as well as some future possible cooperation options.

As the DIDYMOS-XR project did unfortunately not have the possibility to attend the Conference, the projects got to meet in early November.

Martijn Rooker (THEIA^{XR}) and Georg Thallinger ([DIDYMOS-XR](#)) met during an informal meeting introducing the two projects to each other, discussing the status of the project, and looking forward to potential cooperation.

Figure 8: Martijn Rooker and Georg Thallinger at their informal sister project meeting

It was great to now have met all our sister projects and we are looking forward to continuing future cooperation and working together.

NOVEMBER 2023: WUD STUTTART

“COLLABORATION AND COOPERATION”

A perfect headline in the context of every project, especially of EU projects. This time, it was the topic of the 18th annual World Usability Day (WUD) in Stuttgart.

On November 9, 2023, Stuttgart Media University researchers Tanja Brodbeck and Manuel Kulzer attended the event in the Quantum & Artificial Intelligence Experience Center (Q.AX) in Ehningen. There, they held a talk on co-design for

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off-highway vehicles, introducing the THEIA^{XR} project and its use-cases. A special focus was set on the tailoring of user research and design methods meeting the requirements of these special domains.

"So far, the most complex but also most interesting research- and design phase I've participated to..."

This is how Manuel Kulzer from Stuttgart Media University summarizes the preparations of the CoDesign approach involving end user of off-highway machinery in THEIA^{XR}. Together with Tanja Brodbeck, he presented the approach at the World Usability Day WUD Stuttgart.

Figure 9: Tanja Brodbeck and Manuel Kulzer presenting at the "World Usability Day" in Stuttgart

NOVEMBER 2023: CONSORTIUM MEETING

In November, it was time for the second THEIA^{XR} consortium meeting. This time the meeting was hosted by the Technische Universität Dresden in Dresden, Germany.

We had many interesting presentations and got practical insights in many topics that have been progressed in our project:

- ◆ we heard a lot about the respective use case and work package progress
- ◆ many communication topics have been depicted which you can enjoy in the coming weeks and months
- ◆ privacy workshops are on the way to finalisation opening doors for the ongoing work

- ◆ we are ready to kick off the Co-design process where we are inviting the operators to participate to our project.

Figure 10: Impressions from the second consortium meeting in Dresden, Germany

Besides the presentations in the meeting room, we even had the possibility to operate the demo excavator and remote reachstacker.

The colleagues of TU Dresden provided this opportunity by creating a safe environment disabling certain functions and giving the necessary safety instruction. We were able to dig into the earth and get a tiny glimpse of the challenges, operators of these heavy machines may face. Of course, we were also able to experience some of the features suggested and currently tested to support the operators in the future.

Figure 11: Group picture in front of the excavator

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While of course it was a very cool experience and we also had fun during this session, the reason behind is very serious as - regardless the role in the project - it is essential to have a good understanding of all aspects of the work done and support project exchange.

On day two of our consortium meeting and after concluding our presentations and discussions, we were heading to the interaction lab at TU Dresden and it got practical.

- ◆ Practical in a sense of sitting in a cabin that's equipped with external sensors, adapted to data processing for merging the input and highlighted in ambient lightning.
- ◆ Practical in a sense of a demo on remotely operating a reachstacker as if you are picking and placing a container in a harbour.

Figure 12: Gerald Fritz-Mayer remotely operating a reachstacker in virtual reality

NOVEMBER 2023: AGRITECHNICA

"Experience the cabin of the future" is our theme and we are ready to do so at every occasion. So, it was the turn of our project coordinator Martijn Rooker and technical coordinator Gerald Fritz-Mayer to use the visit of the Agritechnica spreading THEIA^{XR} vibes. The Agritechnica proved that agriculture is another domain, where XR can play a significant role in controlling large machinery, like tractors or harvesters.

The discussions covered all from technical deep-dive on XR solutions for the cabin, testing demonstrators of various exhibitors on site and meeting project partners like Creanex on their stands.

Figure 13: Timo Mustonen, Martijn Rooker and Gerald Fritz-Mayer meeting at the Agritechnica

Discussing with the experts during the exhibition, we see the demand depicted in THEIA^{XR} and represented by the selected use cases is as far-reaching and of cross-domain type as we anticipated. Making the invisible visible is a topic for many types of cabins!

NOVEMBER 2023: EUROXR

At the end of November, Kaj Helin was presenting the THEIA^{XR} project at the EuroXR Conference in Rotterdam including several tracks: scientific, application, and porter and demos. It was held at De Doelen, in Rotterdam from November 29th to December 1st 2023 and was also collocated with the Immersive Tech Week.

The presentation "Making the invisible visible for off-highway machinery by conveying extended reality technologies" was part of application track in session "Architecture, Building and Construction" and included an overview of THEIA^{XR} project and more detailed of UI concept development of Kalmar use case.

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Figure 14: Presentation of THEIA^{XR} at EuroXR

DECEMBER 2023: OPERATOR WORKSHOP

In early December, it was time for another operator workshop. This time we got to visit KALMAR in Ljungby, Sweden, for user research on reachstackers in THEIA^{XR}, along with research director Pekka Yli-Paunu. Manuel Kulzer and his team got a pretty awesome tour of the facilities, completed contextual inquiries with two extremely skilled vehicle operators and got to try out one of the machines themselves. The pictures really don't do their actual size justice...

Figure 15: Operator workshop @KALMAR in Sweden

JANUARY 2024: VDBUM

At the 52th VDBUM Großseminar, Volker Waurich presented recent results from the THEIA^{XR} project and gave insights into the application of XR technologies for excavator operation.

Figure 16: Presentation of THEIA^{XR} at VDBUM

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COMING UP

	Dec '24 Stereopsia	

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